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PROSPLIGN

Prospecting natural lignin biodiversity towards unlocking value-added bioactive motifs and molecules

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1 Executive Summary

The renewable, natural, and biocompatible characteristics of lignin represent a fundamental milestone in pharmaceutical, cosmeceutical, and fragrance applications. The widespread availability of lignin, abundant in nature and sourced from low-cost biowaste, has positioned this polymer as one of the most promising elements to explore for replacing common chemical ingredients in the mentioned fields. This preliminary summary report corresponds to the work performed as part of Work Package (WP) 4 “Bioactive molecules screening and purification”, which includes an array of appropriate bioactivity assays to selectively identify relevant activities for pharmaceutical, cosmetic and fragrance applications.

This PUBLIC preliminary report discusses the results arising from the first batches of bioassays performed on small-scale depolymerised lignin samples (mixtures of lignin-derived molecules) arising from the chemical (KELADA) and enzymatic (UH) depolymerisation workflows of WP3. The report highlights the screening efforts carried out by MEDINA in Task 4.1 and 4.2, which aim to identify bioactive compounds with applications in the field of pharmaceuticals and cosmetics, respectively. The screening of 383 depolymerised lignin samples from WP3 resulted in 31 hits with potential antitumoral effect. Importantly, 25 samples showed specificity for melanoma and 3 for pancreatic cancer. We also identified 14 hits with potential anti-infective activity, 1 sample specific for *P.aeruginosa*, 6 samples specific for MSSA, and 7 samples showed specific antifungal effect. Finally, 20 hits were selected for their potential regenerative effect on human fibroblasts. All the hits have been preselected for further fractionation.

The report also summarizes the progress in Task 4.3 carried out by NOVA, which focuses on identifying bioactive compounds for fragrances applications. Of 70 samples already screened, 16 were identified as potential hits. Two hits with higher score were selected for scale-up and fractionation. A second batch of 169 samples is currently under analysis.

Fractionated scale-up samples prepared by BFH in Task 4.4 will be further subjected to bioassays through an iterative process in order to identify fractions containing bioactive compounds which, after isolation, will be characterised by UCD, and ultimately validated for commercial viability with their properties optimised through chemical modification by KELADA.

2 Objectives

This deliverable summarizes the screening efforts developed by MEDINA to identify the primary hits with potential pharmaceutical and cosmetic use, according to the antimicrobial activities on human pathogens and the cytotoxic effect on human tumoral cell lines and to the pro-regenerative effect on human fibroblasts. It also includes the screening experiments conducted by NOVA to identify primary hits with potential applications in the fragrance industry.

3 Screening Methodologies

Within the scope of this report, a total of 383 depolymerised lignin samples from WP3 activities (mixtures of lignin-derived molecules) have been assessed in pharmaceutical, cosmetic, and fragrance bioassays. From those, 379 were prepared by KelAda and shipped in powder format in two separated batches (123 samples and 256 samples), and 4 samples derived from enzymatic depolymerization were prepared by the University of Helsinki (UH).

All samples were kept at -20°C. Samples in powder format were dissolved in DMSO 100% at 10 mg/ml, vortexed, sonicated and filtrated with a 0.22 µm mesh. All samples were dispensed into 384-well plates to enable high throughput screening (HTS) analyses.

3.1 Pharmaceutical bioassays:

3.1.1 Antitumoral assays:

The antitumoral effect of lignin samples was evaluated by assessing the cytotoxicity of each sample in the human tumoral cell lines: HepG2 (hepatoma), MCF-7 (breast cancer), A2058 (melanoma), A549 (lung cancer), and MiaPaca-2 (pancreas cancer).

The cytotoxicity was measured by MTT assay, which is a colorimetric assay that evaluates cellular metabolic activity. NAD(P)H-dependent cellular oxidoreductase enzyme may reflect the number of viable cells present. This enzyme can reduce the tetrazolium dye MTT, 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide, which has a purple color and absorbs at 570 nm.

Cells were cultured for 24 hours before incubating with ligning samples for 72 h. Absorbance at 570 nm was measured by Envision Multiplate Reader (PerkinElmer). The absorbance obtained is directly proportional to the number of living cells and the AC50 (activity concentration at 50% of maximal activity) can be calculated using Genedata Screener software.

Samples prepared in 100% DMSO were tested at dilution 1:200 to final concentration of 0.5% DMSO in the assay and aqueous preparations (UH) were tested at final 2.5%. Results were analyzed using Genedata Screener software and were shown normalized to the negative control 0 (vehicle) and the positive control -100 (MMS). Z'-factor was calculated as well. Z'-Factor is a quality control parameter that reflects the robustness and reproducibility of the assay and is also used for statistical purposes¹.

3.1.2 Anti-infective assays:

The anti-infective effect of lignin samples was evaluated by assessing the antimicrobial activity of each sample in the human pathogens: Gram negative bacteria (*Acinetobacter baumannii* ATCC19606, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* ATCC700603, *Escherichia coli* ATCC25922, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* PAO-1), Gram positive bacteria (*Methicillin Sensitive Staphylococcus aureus* MSSA29213), or fungi (*Aspergillus fumigatus* ATCC46645 and *Candida albicans* ATCC64124).

The antimicrobial effect of each sample was assayed in high throughput liquid-based assays in 96 well plates format, adding 10 μL of lignin extracts (containing 1.6 μL of lignin sample in DMSO 100% and 8.4 μL of media) to 90 μL of the corresponding pathogen culture. Assay conditions were adapted to each of the pathogens. Controls wells were included in each plate using the first and last columns: positive control (100% inhibition growth); growth controls (20% DMSO) (100% total pathogen growth); antibiotic dose-response curve, eight-points at 1/2 serial dilutions. Absorbance at OD 612 nm and fluorescence values were measured with a 2103 EnVision™ Multilabel Plate Readers (Perkin Elmer, Waltham, MA). Genedata Screener software (Genedata, Inc., Basel, Switzerland) was used to process and analyze the data, calculate quality control parameters (RZ' factor and signal-to-background (S/B) ratio). The activity of each sample is expressed as a percentage of inhibition growth, where 100% represented the inhibition growth of the target microorganisms and 0% represented the total growth of target microorganisms on the assay.

3.2 Cosmetic assays:

Cosmetic activity was measured by the ability of lignin-derived samples to promote fibroblast proliferation in culture. The human fibroblast cell line CCD-1064sk (CRL-2076, ATCC) was seeded in 384-well plates (black/clear plate, Greiner) and cultured overnight at 37°C. After 24 h, cells were treated with each lignin-derived sample per duplicate at a dilution 1:200 and vehicle (DMSO 0.5% and water 2.5%) as control and incubated for 48 h. Next, cells were stained with 8 μM Hoechst diluted in PBS for 30 minutes at room temperature in darkness. Then, images were acquired with Operetta CLS High Content Analysis System (Revvity) and analyzed with the Harmony software (Revvity). Results were analyzed using Genedata Screener software as the percentage of cells in each treated well relative to control (vehicle).

3.3 Fragrance assays:

A total of 239 lignin-derived samples were assessed for fragrance potential. Of these, 235 were prepared by KelAda and shipped in two separated batches (66 and 169 samples, respectively). The 4 remaining samples, obtained by enzymatic depolymerisation, were prepared by the UH. Stock solutions of KelAda samples were prepared in a suitable solvent and then further dissolved in an aqueous buffer to obtain working solutions. Working solutions were dispensed into 384-well plates and analysed using a method previously developed by NOVA.

Identified hits were further characterized through dose-response curves. For these, the IC50 values were determined and used to rank the hits accordingly.

4 Results

4.1 Pharmaceutical activity:

4.1.1 Antitumoral assay:

Batch 1 (123 samples from KelAda and 4 samples from UH): Values lower than -70 were considered active. Samples which showed activity against more than two tumoral cell lines or show cytotoxicity for HepG2 (threshold -50) are not interesting because they are highly cytotoxic. 15 samples were cytotoxic (HepG2), 36 samples showed toxicity for all cell lines, and most samples were toxic for three cell lines. Cytotoxic samples for each cell line are listed below:

- HepG2: 12 samples
- MCF-7: 14 samples
- A2058: 13 samples
- A549: 14 samples
- MiaPaca-2: 12 samples

Conclusion: Only two samples that showed selectivity for MiaPaca-2 were selected for further analysis.

Batch 2 (256 samples from KelAda): Values lower than -70 were considered active. In this batch, less toxicity was observed. Only 5 samples showed cytotoxicity (threshold -50) in HepG2. Cytotoxic samples for each cell line are listed below:

- HepG2: 5 samples
- MCF-7: 9 samples
- A2058: 34 samples
- A549: 0 samples
- MiaPaca-2: 8 samples

Conclusion: 29 samples were selected for further studies based on their selective activity for one cell line. Specifically, 25 samples were specific for A2058, 3 were specific for MiaPaca, and one sample was specific for A2058 and MCF-7. None of the selected samples showed cytotoxicity for HepG2, which is the gold standard for in vitro drug toxicology studies.

4.1.2 Anti-infective assays.

Batch 1 (123 samples from KelAda): Values lower than -70 were considered active. Cytotoxic samples for each pathogen are listed below:

- Acinetobacter baumannii: 22 samples
- Klebsiella pneumoniae: 15 samples
- Escherichia coli: 13 samples

- *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*: 20 samples
- *MSSA*: 18 samples
- *Aspergillus fumigatus*: 23 samples
- *Candida albicans*: 37 samples

Conclusion: No sample was selected in this assay because there was no selectivity for a single pathogen or pathogen type (Gram negative, gram positive, and fungi). All positive samples showed activity in at least three different pathogens from different classes.

Batch 2 (256 samples from KelAda): Values lower than -70 were considered active. Active samples against each pathogen are listed below:

- *Acinetobacter baumannii*: 1 sample
- *Klebsiella pneumoniae*: 1 sample
- *Escherichia coli*: 0 samples
- *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*: 1 sample
- *MSSA*: 8 samples
- *Aspergillus fumigatus*: 9 samples
- *Candida albicans*: 47 samples

Conclusion: 14 samples were selected based on their selective activity for one pathogen. Specifically, 1 sample showed specific activity for *P.aeruginosa*, 6 samples showed specific activity for *MSSA* 7 samples were selected for specific antifungal effect (*A. fumigatus* and *C.albicans*). None of them showed cytotoxicity for HepG2.

4.2 Cosmetic assays:

Batch 1 (123 samples from KelAda): Values greater than 30 were considered active (promote proliferation). 10 samples showed proliferative activity, however, standard deviation was unacceptable between replicates, therefore, none of them was selected for further analyses.

Batch 2 (256 samples from KelAda): Values greater than 30 were considered active (promote proliferation). **20 samples were considered active** and selected for further analyses.

4.3 Fragrance assays:

Batch 1 (66 samples from KelAda; 4 samples from UH): A total of 16 hits were identified. For these, dose response curves were performed and IC50 values determined. Two samples with lower IC50 values were selected for further analysis.

Batch 2 (169 samples from KelAda): The analysis is ongoing.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The initial results of the bioassays are encouraging, with good overall trends in bioactivity observed. The samples screened thus far in the project are from preliminary small-scale experiments and consist of small molecules derived from the WP3 lignin depolymerisation work flows. The samples with the most attractive bioactivity profiles have been selected for scale-up to produce sufficiently large quantities for fractionation/purification by BFH and characterisation by UCD.

Specifically, **31 samples** have been selected for further studies based on their selective **antitumoral activity**, **14 samples** have been selected based on their **anti-infective activity**, **20 samples** have been selected based on their potential for **cosmetic activity**, and **2 samples** have been selected for further analyses based on their **activity for fragrance**.

6 References

1. Iversen PW, Eastwood BJ, Sittampalam GS, Cox KL. A comparison of assay performance measures in screening assays: Signal window, Z' factor, and assay variability ratio. J Biomol Screen. 2006;11(3).